

**DETERMINATION OF ASSERTIVENESS AND LONELINESS
STATUS OF STUDENTS AT ÖMER HALISDEMİR UNIVERSITY
PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TEACHING AND
COACHING EDUCATION DEPARTMENT**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the assertiveness and loneliness status of Ömer Halisdemir University Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training and Coaching Education Department. 200 students participated in the research. The loneliness levels of the students were assessed using the 20-item "UCLA Loneliness Scale" (University of California Los Angeles Loneliness Scale) originally developed by Russel, Peplau and Ferguson in 1978 and adapted to Turkish by Demir (1989). The survey was adapted to Turkish by Demir (1998). In the reliability study of the scale, there was a correlation of .91 between the first form and the revised form in 1980. The internal consistency coefficient was .94. In the study for the reliability of the scale, Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was found 96, the test-retest method applied after five-week interval was found to have a correlation coefficient of .94. According to the results of the research, no significant difference was found between the genders of students and assertiveness and loneliness levels, no significant difference was found between the departments of the students and the levels of assertiveness and loneliness, but a significant difference was found between the ages of the students and the levels of assertiveness and loneliness.

Keywords: sport, assertiveness, loneliness

1. Introduction

In recent years, studies on various groups in our country have shown that communication problems in family, school and business life are high. These communication problems are expressed as: not being able to speak in the community, hesitating to make friends with the opposite sex, not being able to discuss the problems with the parents, not being able to express feelings and thoughts clearly, being

incapable of speaking comfortably, not being able to speak with older people as age and social status, not being able to enter a friend group (Ayaz 2002; Kaplanoğlu, 2006).

The necessity of eliminating emotional, social, and physiological needs of individuals is the basis of their behavior. Individuals are constantly in contact with people around them to meet these needs. During this communication, emotion, desire and information are expressed by different forms of behavior. Some individuals are aggressive in relation to their surroundings; they have a tendency to break others, to look down on others and to ignore them in order to meet their needs and to get what they want. Some individuals are so shy that they can not reach their goals, they have difficulty in meeting their needs, for this reason they are often filled with anxiety or anger. The assertiveness, defined as the ability of the person to protect his rights without denying other people's rights, looking down on them as well as timidity and aggressiveness, is a proper communication kind of interpersonal communication types (Örgün 2000; Kaplanoğlu 2006).

Behaviors among people are divided into four groups by Bond: assertive, passive, aggressive and indirect (manipulative). This classification is not a classification of personality structure but is used to classify individual communication examples (Üstün, 1995; Özdağ, 1999; Ayaz, 2002; Bal, 2003; Kaplanoğlu, 2006).

2. Materials and Methods

The aim of this study is to determine the assertiveness and loneliness of the students of Niğde University Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training and Coaching Education Department. 200 students studying in Niğde University Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training and Coaching Education Department participated in the research.

2.1 UCLA Loneliness Scale

The loneliness levels of the students were assessed using the 20-item "UCLA Loneliness Scale" originally developed by Russel, Peplau and Ferguson in 1978 and adapted to Turkish by Demir (1989) (University of California Los Angeles Loneliness Scale). Demir (1998) adapted the survey to Turkish.

Rating of loneliness scales: The UCLA loneliness scale consists of 20 items, 10 of which are straight and 10 of which are coded in the opposite direction. Individuals are asked to specify how often they live the conditions in the materials on a quadruple Likert-type scale. Scale is rated as; items with positive expressions, "never living" 4, "rarely living" 3, "sometimes living" 2, "frequently living" 1 point; materials with negative expressions, on the other hand, "never living" 1, "rarely living" 2, "sometimes living" 3, "frequently living" 4 points. The highest score that can be taken from the scale is 80 and the lowest score is 20. As the score of the scale increases, the level of loneliness also increases (Demir, 1989).

In the reliability study of the scale, there was a correlation of .91 between the first form and the reviewed form in 1980. The internal consistency coefficient was .94. In the study done for the reliability of the scale, The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was found as .96, the correlation coefficient which was obtained using the test-retest method used after five weeks was found .94.

In Turkey, UCLA Loneliness Scale study with similar scale validity was conducted by Demir (1989). Beck Depression Inventory, which is frequently used in the validity study of the UCLA Loneliness Scale, was taken with a scale similar to the Social Introversion subscale of the Multiple Depression Scale developed by Aydın and Demir (1988), and the correlation of Social Introversion subscale was found .82 and Beck Depression Inventory was found .77.

2.2 Rathus Assertiveness Inventory

Several scales have been developed to measure assertiveness in interpersonal relationships. Among these scales, Wolpe-Lazarus Assertiveness Inventory, Rathus Assertiveness Inventory, College Self-Recognition Scale are widely used. However, Rathus Assertiveness Inventory has some advantages, such as its ability to adapt to different cultures, the emergence of shortness, and the ease of evaluation, while measuring the assertiveness compared to other scales (Dinçer 2008).

Rathus Assertiveness Inventory was developed by Rathus in 1973. The inventory which can be applied to adults and adolescents consists of 30 items. Each statement describes the behavior of the individual and scores between -3 and +3. These +3 fit very well with me, +2 they fit quite well, +1 they fit a little bit, -3 they never fit me, -2 they do not quite fit me, -1 they do not really fit me. While rating if the items are marked as -3 or +3, the values of these items are reversed in the scale, in other words, -3s become +3, +3s become -3. The total score of the inventory is obtained by collecting the minus and plus points separately and subtracting from each other. The total points that can be taken range from -90 to +90. . It is evaluated as assertive between +10 and +90 points and shy behaviour between -90 and +10 points according to the score obtained from the scale (Volcan 1980).

Rathus (1973) found a reliability coefficient of 0.76 and a validity coefficient of 0.70 using a test re-test method -giving 15 days break- for the reliability test of the inventory (Tan 2006). RAE's validity and reliability study of Turkey was done by Volta (1980) (Appendix 3). Volcan (1980) conducted a study with a 15-day break on the 37 students who are at 3rd grade at Hacettepe University Department of Child Development, he found the test-retest reliability coefficient of the inventory using the Pearson Moments Correlation Formula as 0.92, the internal consistency coefficient of the test divided by the Spearman Brown technique as 0.77 (Volcan, 1980).

The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency rates of the Rathus Assertiveness Inventory were found by Kaplanoğlu (2005) 0,72, Timuçin (2005) 0,82 and Yıldız (2006) 0,82, and Kutlu (0,08). The Cronbachalpha rate was found to be 0.78 in our study and it was found to be a safe scale for our study.

3. Findings

Table 1: Gender, age and department information of students

		N	%
Gender	Female	108	54,0
	Male	92	46,0
Department	Coaching	108	54,0
	Physical education and sports teacher	92	46,0
Age	20	48	24,0
	21	64	32,0
	22	45	22,5
	23	16	8,0
	24	11	5,5
	25	16	8,0

According to Table 1, 54% of the students are female, 46% are male; 54% of them are studying in coaching education, 46% of them are in physical education and sport teacher education; 24% are 20 years old, 32% are 21, 22,5% are 21, 8% are 23, 5.5% are 24 and 8% are 25 years old.

Table 2: Status of students' genders according to UCLA Loneliness Scale and Rathus Assertiveness Scale scores

	Gender	N	X	ss	t	p
UCLA	Female	108	52,4444	4,87092	-1,637	,103
	Male	92	53,5978	5,07539		
RATHUS	Female	108	14,4074	25,07895	,927	,356
	Male	92	11,1522	24,51684		

According to Table 2, no significant difference was found between the sexes of the students and the levels of assertiveness and loneliness.

Table 3: Status of students' the department according to UCLA Loneliness Scale and Rathus Assertiveness Scale scores

	Department	N	X	ss	t	p
UCLA	Coaching	108	52,74	4,75	-,719	,473
	Physical education and sports teacher	92	53,25	5,25		
RATHUS	Coaching	108	14,14	24,99	,764	,446
	Physical education and sports teacher	92	11,45	24,65		

According to Table 3, no significant difference was found between the departments of the students and the levels of assertiveness and loneliness.

Table 4: Status of students' ages according to UCLA Loneliness Scale and Rathus Assertiveness Scale scores

		Average Square	SD	Total Square	F	P
UCLA	Intergroups	514,827	5	102,965	4,505	,001

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	Intragroups	4434,048	194	22,856		
	Total	4948,875	199			
RATHUS	Intergroups	12785,075	5	2557,015	4,520	,001
	Intragroups	109737,305	194	565,656		
	Total	122522,380	199			

According to Table 4, there was a significant difference between the ages of the students and the levels of assertiveness and loneliness.

4. Discussion

The purpose of this study is to determine the assertiveness and loneliness status of the students of the Physical Education and Sports Teaching and Coaching Education Department of Niğde University Physical Education and Sports College. 200 students studying in Niğde University Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training and Coaching Education Department participated in the research.

54% of the students were female, 46% were male; 54% were in coaching education, 46% were in physical education and sport teacher education; 24% are 20 years old, 32% are 21 years old, 22,5% are 21 years old, 8% are 23 years old, 5.5% are 24 years old and 8% are 25 years old. According to the results of the research, no significant difference was found between the sexes of students and assertiveness and loneliness levels, there was no significant difference between departments of the students and levels of assertiveness and loneliness, but a significant difference was found between ages and assertiveness and loneliness levels.

Demir (1990) found that male university students had more loneliness than female students in their study of loneliness levels in terms of various variables. Çeçen (2007) also found similar results in a study of university students studying social and emotional loneliness according to their gender and life satisfaction levels. A similar study was conducted by Karaoğlu, Avşaroğlu, Deniz (2009); in the study, the relationship between feelings of loneliness and gender, age and some socio-demographic data was evaluated in university students: male students' loneliness levels were found to be statistically significantly higher than girls; it was found that the level of loneliness was positively affected by satisfaction with the environment. However, other socio-demographic variables were not effective on loneliness level.

According to the results of the studies of Ayaz (2002) on nurses, Kaplanoğlu (2006) and Timuçin (2005) on executive nurses they did not find any significant difference between age and assertiveness point averages. According to Bal (2003) the average of assertiveness scores of nurses at the age of 40 and over, according to Timuçin (2005) the average of assertiveness scores of nurses over 43 years was found to decrease. This is similar to the finding of our work. However, according to Kaplanoğlu's (2006) study results it was observed that the assertiveness score averages of executive nurses aged 40 years and over were higher than the average scores of the other groups.

According to the researcher of İşgör (2003) on the adolescents who work and do not work, found that adolescents who work in a job while studying have lower levels of assertiveness than those who do not work. This situation is explained by the fact that the adolescents whose academic achievements are found to be low have a negative image of the self-image, which may adversely affect the level of assertiveness of the adolescent.

Güler, Aydos and Koç (2005) investigated the effects of 6th, 7th and 8th grade students of state primary schools in different socio-economical levels on their assertiveness of their participation in education and sports activities. the education and training activities in the second level of the state primary schools do not sufficiently affect the assertiveness levels of the students in the interclass context; it was determined that participation in sporting activities had an impact and that assertive behaviors developed more in children participating in sporting activities.

Ersan and Dogan (2002) concluded that, as a result of studying the relationship between assertiveness and aggression levels in physical education and sport college students with socio-demographic characteristics, it was found that the assertiveness and aggression scores of the team athletes were higher than those of the individual athletes and that the score of destructive aggression was higher in males than in females and it was emphasized that this could be due to cultural factors especially gender discrimination in child raising.

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